

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR TRANSPORT AIRCRAFT, MARINE, AND CIVIL STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Organic matrix composites are emerging as a strong contender for a wide variety of transport aircraft, marine, and civil structures. High performance fibers embedded in polymeric matrices produce composite structural materials which have specific tensile and compressive properties 5 to 10 times that of conventional structural steels. Stiffnesses are tailored by controlling fiber/ply directions which provides significant structural advantage. Weight savings with composite structures should be at least 33%, and more typically 70% to 80%. Additionally, organic matrix composites have excellent fatigue properties and do not corrode, providing a significant maintenance cost saving. Composites have found increasing use in military aircraft, approaching 50% of the structural weight. Acquisition cost has traditionally been relatively high, hindering widespread use of composites outside relatively low volume military applications. The key to widespread use of composites in transport aircraft, marine, and civil applications is to focus on high throughput, continuous, automated processing. By reaching the right threshold cost, composites will be more attractive and we will see significant increases in applications. Transport aircraft applications alone would dwarf the military composite usage. Potential marine applications include ship and submarine superstructures, hulls, casings, pipes, machinery, decks, radomes, masts, propellers, shafts, and control surfaces. Civil structure applications could be the largest potential market of all, including bridge structural components, decks, building structural components, pressure vessels, chemical plant components, and pipelines. This paper will explore these areas and the breakthroughs which are coming that will cause significant increase in the use of composites.

Fighter Aircraft Composite Structures Development

McDonnell Douglas Aerospace (MDA) began development work on resin matrix composites in the 1960's with the boron-epoxy rudder for the F-4 Phantom II. The high specific stiffness of boron made this material a prime choice for control surfaces, designed primarily by flutter/aeroelastic requirements. The F-15 Eagle empennage was designed with boron-epoxy skins bonded to full-depth honeycomb and to titanium "picture frames". Boron-epoxy is still used for this application and is optimum from a weight standpoint because of its high specific stiffness.

The advent of lower-cost carbon fiber marked the gradual reduction in the use of boron fiber. As the carbon fiber market grew, the price differential increased, approaching a factor of ten. MDA's initial carbon-epoxy development was the F-15 speedbrake, which has carbon-epoxy skins cocured to full-depth honeycomb, with titanium hinge fittings. An early R&D program was also performed on the

F-15 wing, with the technology lessons learned being implemented on the F/A-18. The F/A-18 Hornet marked the first production implementation of carbon-epoxy in primary structure (mid 1970's), with thick wing skins containing very complex ply drop-offs and bonded step-lap splice fittings. Other carbon-epoxy F/A-18 applications include the trailing edge flaps, speedbrake, stabilator skins, fin skins, rudders, covers, and access doors (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Composites Applications
F/A-18 Hornet

The AV-8B Harrier II development marked the most extensive implementation of composites at that time (late 1970's). Performance requirements for a vertical take-off fighter mandates a strong emphasis on weight reduction. The AV-8B (Figure 2) employs carbon-epoxy for the wing torque box, forward fuselage, rudder, stabilizer, flaps, ailerons, overwing fairings, outrigger fairings, and engine access doors. The wing torque box is carbon-epoxy sine-wave spars with full-span skins (Figure 3). The integral hat-stiffened composite forward fuselage is built in subassemblies. The AV-8B stabilator construction (Figure 4) utilizes cocurred lower skin and integral spars plus a concurrently cured upper skin, similar to the flap and aileron. The upper skin is cured with the rest of the stabilator, but mechanically fastened to allow inspection and to provide supportability. The first production application for high-temperature carbon-bismaleimide (C-BMI) was the AV-8B strakes (early 80's), which have high temperature air impingement from the nozzles. Higher cure temperatures for C-BMI required special process development, with good results, evidenced by the AV-8B production implementation. Other AV-8B bismaleimide structures include the gun and ammo packs, and the trailing edge flap lower skin.

Future advanced fighters will make even more extensive use of thermoset and thermoplastic composites, approaching 50% composites by weight. While automation of manufacturing processes is a cost reduction goal for many technologies, it is vital to production implementation of thermoplastic composites (TPC) and full realization of TPC processing capabilities. The combination of instantaneous processing, with the application of heat and pressure, and the dry, boardy material forms demand automation to capture the full advantages of TPC.

Figure 2. Composites Applications
AV-8B Harrier II

Figure 3. AV-8B Harrier Composite Wing

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Figure 4. AV-8B Harrier Composite Horizontal Stabilizer

MDA is developing a number of automated thermoset and thermoplastic processing technologies for advanced aircraft and other applications. These technologies include fiber placement, thermoforming, diaphragm forming, compression molding, injection molding, pultrusion, resin transfer molding, automated ply lamination, joining, and handling. High-rate, automated fiber placement technology is being developed for production of complex contoured structures. Work with complex woven preforms has included thermoformed and pultruded structures and has shown high potential for reduced material handling and low-cost processing. Various robotic techniques for fusion joining assemblies are being studied. MDA is automating the engineering side of composite processing, through the development of computer process models, and integrating engineering, procurement, quality, and manufacturing via the Integrated Composites Center.

A systematic, building-block approach has been used by MDA on all aerospace programs to develop the design, analysis, and manufacturing technologies needed to implement production use of resin matrix composites in fighter aircraft primary structure applications. Use of resin matrix composites in areas beyond aerospace is increasing because their excellent specific properties permit weight savings and performance improvements. Life-cycle cost savings accrue from both reduced fuel usage and reduced maintenance, since composites have excellent corrosion and fatigue resistance. Technology development is continuing, focusing on tougher materials with improved strength and stiffness, and process improvements to produce high-quality, low-cost structural components. Automated fabrication and inspection equipment development is key to achieving cost and quality goals on aerospace and other applications and has been a central focus for MDA for over twenty-five years.

Transport Aircraft Composite Structures Development

Both military and commercial transport aircraft have been much slower in utilizing composite structures due primarily to concerns about cost and schedule risk in scaling up to the larger components. Composites are in widespread use for secondary structure applications including control surfaces like flaps, ailerons, stabilizers, and rudders. An early development program which showed the benefits of organic composites for transport aircraft was the DC-10 rudder (Figure 5). This all composite postbuckled design has been in service for 20 years with excellent service experience. Airbus Industries has been the most aggressive in incorporating composites, reaching 15% composites by weight on the A340. Deutsche Aerospace has developed an exciting Integrated Tape Laying System which includes an automated design program (LaGrange) which can drive an automated tape steering machine to produce optimized lightweight structure (Figure 6). These methods reduce the cost and schedule risk of large structures and will allow significant increase in composite utilization. Transport aircraft composite utilization could reach the 30 to 40% range, which would result in an order of magnitude increase in the volume of composite material required and a potential material cost reduction through volume. Future increases in the price of jet fuel will spur the use of composites in transport aircraft structure. Business jets have been very aggressive in applying composites, since the translation from fighter aircraft is much more direct.

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Figure 5. DC-10 Aircraft With Composite Rudder

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Figure 6. Composite Tape Laying Systems

Marine Applications

Low cost/low performance organic composites have dominated the small pleasure craft business for some time. Low cure temperature resins like vinyl esters/sheet molding compound are typically used with glass fibers. Manufacturing processes are typically appropriate for high volume and include wet lay-up, spray coating, compression molding, etc. Composite benefits include ability to mold complex integral shapes, smooth durable finish, corrosion resistance, and ability to fabricate low cost stiff sandwich structures. Continuous high performance fibers have been used very little, but material cost reduction will show significant benefits for use in selected areas.

A number of larger composite vessels have been fabricated including minesweepers (Figure 7). Thermoplastic composites were used for the rudder on the hovercraft (Figure 8) because of its excellent durability and resistance to erosion. Glass reinforced plastic has been used for mine hunters because it is nonmagnetic, non-conducting, low maintenance, and has better explosion resistance. Single-skin stiffened construction has been used by the United Kingdom, Spain, France, Netherlands, Belgium, and Finland. Foam construction has been employed by Sweden, Denmark, Australia, and Norway. Thick unstiffened monocoque construction has been used by the United States, Italy, Malaysia and Korea. The advantages and disadvantages of these alternate methods of construction are still being evaluated. Widespread use on larger vessels awaits development of low cost materials and out-of-autoclave processes to avoid the need for large capital expenditures. Besides the benefits previously mentioned, reduction in topside weight can improve stability of the vessel and will therefore replace aluminum in ship superstructures. Durable, fatigue-resistant composite hulls can be designed using single hull, double hull, and sandwich concepts. Double hull tankers with energy absorbing composite outer hulls would reduce the threat of oil spills. Propeller shafts, tanks and pressure vessels have been successfully fabricated from composites and show significant performance benefits. Corrosion elimination should make utilization of composites very attractive for future ship and submarine applications.

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Figure 7. Minesweeper Hull

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Figure 8. Hovercraft

Civil Applications

Potential civil structure applications include bridges, bridge decks, standard shapes, antennae's, modular sections for cooling towers, roof structures, chemical plants, curtain walls, non-conductive high voltage rail covers, rail cars, rail support structures, storage tanks, buses, trucks, floor grating, medical implants, and tunnels. Corrosion resistance alone would be enough of a driver, since metallic corrosion of civil structures in the US is estimated at \$200 Billion per year. While there has been some early work directed towards composite civil structures much additional work is needed.

The main barrier to the structural use of advanced composites has been the cost of these materials relative to the traditional civil structural materials of steel, concrete, and timber. However, emerging technology is providing lower cost materials and more efficient, automated manufacturing methods for producing composite structural shapes. Composite materials are very resistant to environmental effects; that is, they will not corrode and deteriorate like steel, concrete, and timber do. Composite materials are also fatigue resistant; that is, repeated application of loads will not result in a failure at a load level very close to the initial strength of the structure (very high endurance limit). Metal structures, like steel, can experience fatigue failures well below their initial static strength. Using a material that is resistant to the environment and is fatigue resistant will result in civil structures with increased life spans and reduced maintenance requirements. Thus, more affordable acquisition costs coupled with lower life cycle costs could result in composite civil structures that are much more cost effective than traditional, present-day civil structures.

A consortium/team approach is needed with prospective users, engineers, industry, universities, standards organizations, government, architects and material suppliers working together to develop new codes, identify criteria, develop and evaluate prototypes, and to develop low cost materials and automated processes.

Summary

In the last quarter century we have seen significant growth in the use of organic composites in aerospace structures. Composites have excellent specific strength and stiffness, corrosion resistance, tailorability, durability, and fatigue resistance. The potential to significantly reduce acquisition cost must be aggressively pursued so that much broader application to transport aircraft, marine, and civil structures is realized. By reaching the right threshold cost, composites will be more attractive and we will see significant increase in applications.

MARINE APPLICATIONS
